

Enabling Code_Saturne for Multi-Petaflop/Exascale with MPI 3.0 one sided Communication

Chandan Basu^{a,1}, Soon-Heum Ko^a, Charles Moulinec^b, Yvan Fournier^c

^aNational Supercomputer Centre, Sweden

^bSTFC, Daresbury Laboratory, UK

^cEDF R&D, France

Abstract

Code_Saturne is a popular open-source computational fluid dynamics package. We have carried out a study of applying MPI 2.0 / MPI 3.0 one sided communication routines to *Code_Saturne* and its impact on improving the scalability of the code for future peta/exascale. We have developed modified versions of the halo exchange routine in *Code_Saturne*. Our modifications showed that MPI 2.0 one sided calls give some speed improvement and less memory overhead compared to the original version. The MPI 3.0 version on the other hand is unstable and could not run.

Application Code: *Code_Saturne*

1. Introduction

The computational capabilities of large supercomputers are increasing rapidly and are expected to reach exascale range by year 2020 [1]. This development raises significant challenge for the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) applications for utilizing such resources. *Code_Saturne* [2] is a well known open-source code for solving Navier-Stokes equations in 2D, 2D-axisymmetric and 3D flows. It can handle steady or unsteady, laminar or turbulent, incompressible, compressible or weakly dilatible, isothermal or non-isothermal cases. *Code_Saturne* has been chosen for the short list of software gathered in the PRACE Benchmark Suite as one of the two CFD application tools [3] and extensive work has been undertaken within PRACE [5-6] to optimize *Code_Saturne*.

Code_Saturne is an MPI parallelized code. Its scalability depends on the MPI communication efficiency and how loaded each MPI task is. In the newly released MPI 3.0 standard [7] many new features have been introduced for better scalability of codes, e.g., improved remote memory access (RMA) one-sided communication routines, non-blocking collectives. This is expected to greatly enhance the scalability and performance of MPI-3.0 compared to MPI-2.0 [8].

Substantial communication overhead of *Code_Saturne* comes from halo exchange between neighbouring subdomains/processors. Halo exchange in *Code_Saturne* is implemented by MPI_Isend, MPI_Irecv and MPI_Wait routines. In this project we have investigated the impact of replacing these MPI point to point routines with MPI 2.0 / MPI 3.0 one sided routines. The lower overhead associated with one-sided communication as compared to two-sided communication has the potential to increase the performance at peta/exascale by increasing the effective network bandwidth and reducing synchronization overheads.

2. Profiling of Code_Saturne

Code_Saturne is a very large software package and it is difficult to know at first which routine is the most suitable for applying MPI one sided communication. For this purpose we have done profiling of the code to

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* Corresponding author. E-mail address: cbasu@nsc.liu.se

identify communication intensive routines. This has given us an idea about which routines are using MPI point-to-point calls and what their overhead is.

Profiling with TAU & gprof

Profiling tools of gprof and TAU [9] have been used for finding the hot-spots of the code. TAU is famous for providing detailed information about computation and communication intensive routines. However in our profiling of *Code_Saturne* we observed that TAU-compiled executable failed to produce any profiling result. We believe this is due to some bug in TAU. This issue has been also addressed in another PRACE task [10]. Therefore we based on gprof tool for detecting hot-spots of the code.

The GNU gprof profiling tool is a simple utility for code profiling. GNU-provided gprof is frequently used for light-weight profiling since it is portable with most application codes. *Code_Saturne* is compiled and linked with additional -g and -pg flag for using gprof. *Code_Saturne* is then run as usual. After the run is over profile files are generated. For parallel jobs we set the environment variable GMON_OUT_PREFIX=name, where 'name' is the prefix of the name of the profile files. The generated profile names are, e.g., name.xxx where xxx is the rank number of a process. The profile files are then converted to text files using the command

```
$gprof cs_solver name.xxx > profile.xxx
```

The profile.xxx files contain the timing information for different routines. It also shows the call graphs of different routines, e.g., for the halo exchange routine `cs_halo_sync_var` the call graph looks like:

index	%time	self time	child time	called	name
		0.00	0.00	1/50342	cs_mesh_quantities_compute [104]
		0.00	0.00	40/50342	cs_mesh_sync_var_scal_ext [318]
		0.00	0.00	120/50342	cs_grid_coarsen [50]
		0.01	0.00	292/50342	cs_mesh_sync_var_scal [273]
		0.01	0.00	353/50342	cgdcel_ [18]
		0.01	0.00	414/50342	cs_mesh_sync_var_vect_ni [222]
		1.29	0.01	49122/50342	cs_halo_sync_component [42]
[41]	1.5	1.32	0.01	50342	cs_halo_sync_var [41]
		0.01	0.00	1006840/1041650	MPI_Isend [270]
		0.00	0.00	1006840/1041650	MPI_Irecv [401]
		0.00	0.00	50342/52084	MPI_Waitall [406]

Figure 1: call graph of `cs_halo_sync_var`

In Figure 1 the 1st column is the function index, the 2nd column gives the percentage of elapsed time out of total runtime. Columns 3 and 4 show the percentage of elapsed time in self & child routines. The 5th column in Figure 1 shows how many times these routines are called and the total number of calls. The 6th column gives the name of the routines. In figure 1, routines above `cs_halo_sync_var` are the routines calling it and the routines below `cs_halo_sync_var` are the routines called by it. We can see that `cs_halo_sync_var` calls `MPI_Isend`, `MPI_Irecv` and `MPI_Waitall`. From Figure 1 we can see that `cs_halo_sync_var` is called 50342 times while `cs_halo_sync_var` calls `MPI_Isend` 1006840 times out of total 1041650 calls of `MPI_Isend`. Similarly `cs_halo_sync_var` calls `MPI_Irecv` 1006840 times out of total 1041650 calls of `MPI_Irecv` and `MPI_Waitall` 50342 times out of total 52084 calls of `MPI_Waitall`. This shows that most of the `MPI_Isend`, `MPI_Irecv` and `MPI_Waitall` calls are from the `cs_halo_sync_var` routine. However timings shown in columns 2 – 4 are not accurate as gprof can not show the MPI timings correctly as the MPI libraries are not compiled with -g and -pg flags. That is why self and child times of MPI routines are shown as zero in this table. To get the MPI timing correctly we use a simple tool developed by us. We have a precompiled library of `MPI_Wrapper` routines. An example of `MPI_Waitall` wrapper routine is given below:

```

int MPI_Waitall_prof(int count, MPI_Request *array_of_requests,
                    MPI_Status *array_of_statuses){
    int res;
    TIMER1;
    res = MPI_Waitall(count, array_of_requests, array_of_statuses);
    TIMER2;
    t_waitall = t_waitall + TIME_DIFF;
    n_waitall = n_waitall + 1;
    return res;
}

```

Most other MPI routines are wrapped in a similar way. The original library calls are substituted by symbolic replacement during compilation. As an example to replace `MPI_Waitall` with our wrapper we pass additional command line flags `"-DMPI_Waitall=MPI_Waitall_prof"`. This replaces all the occurrences of `MPI_Waitall` by `MPI_Waitall_prof`. Finally while linking we add our MPI wrapper library. When this binary is run every MPI call is instrumented and the cumulative time for each MPI routine is printed at the end of the run. This tool is a simple and adaptable tool which can be used as a starting tool before trying more rigorous profiling tools. For *Code_Saturne* run the MPI profile is shown in Figure 2.

```

rank 0 MPI_Total(s) 152.499371 (100.000000% of tot) for 1 times
rank 0 MPI_Waitall(s) 3.775951 (6.476044% of tot) for 52084 times
rank 0 MPI_Reduce(s) 0.378624 (0.248279% of tot) for 6 times
rank 0 MPI_Allreduce(s) 18.978851 (12.445200% of tot) for 100419 times
rank 0 MPI_Sendrecv(s) 0.025146 (0.016489% of tot) for 36 times
rank 0 MPI_Send(s) 0.022175 (0.014541% of tot) for 2 times
rank 0 MPI_Recv(s) 0.002828 (0.001854% of tot) for 16 times

```

Figure 2: MPI profiling results for rank 0

In Figure 2 `MPI_Total` is the total run time between `MPI_Init` and `MPI_Finalize`. We can see in Figure 2 that `MPI_Waitall` amounts for 6.47 % of the total run time. In the above Figure 2 `MPI_Isend`, `MPI_Irecv` times are not seen as these are non blocking calls and consequently do not take any significant time. We also see that `MPI_Allreduce` is the most expensive MPI routine in the run, due to the use of linear solvers. However in this work we do not focus on collective communications as we are interested in replacing MPI point to point calls by MPI one sided calls.

From the discussions above we see that the routine `cs_halo_sync_var` is the heaviest user of `MPI_Isend`, `MPI_Irecv` and `MPI_Waitall` routines. Hence we have implemented MPI one sided communication the routine `cs_halo_sync_var`.

3. Development activities

From our profiling results we see that the `cs_halo_sync_var` routine is the best candidate for trying one sided MPI 3.0 communication routines. However not many implementations of MPI 3.0 standard are available as of now. To the best of our knowledge open-source `mvapich2` [11] and `MPICH` [12] have full support for MPI 3.0 standard while `OpenMPI` [13] has partial support of MPI 3.0. We have chosen `mvapich2` as our choice of MPI 3.0 implementation as it is highly optimized for infiniband clusters. For our development activities we use the `Triolith` cluster [14] at the National Supercomputer Centre (NSC), Sweden.

Structure of original `cs_halo_sync_var` routine

For modifying the `cs_halo_sync_var` we first need to understand the original routine. The `cs_halo_sync_var` routine performs halo exchange between neighbouring ranks. The receiver ranks first post non-blocking receive request for data from the neighbouring ranks. The pseudo code is given in Figure 3.

```

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];
    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
        MPI_Irecv(var + halo->n_local_elts + start,
                length,
                CS_MPI_REAL,
                halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
                halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
                cs_glob_mpi_comm,
                &(_cs_glob_halo_request[request_count++]));
    }
    else
        local_rank_id = rank_id;
}

```

Figure 3 Pseudo code for receive request in original `cs_halo_sync_var`

Then sender ranks assemble send buffers for halo exchange into a contiguous buffer called `build_buffer` as shown in Figure 4.

```

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift]
            - halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
    for (i = 0; i < length; i++)
        build_buffer[start + i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];
}

```

Figure 4: Pseudo code for data copy in a contiguous buffer in original `cs_halo_sync_var`

Then the sender ranks send data from `build_buffer` to neighbouring ranks which is shown in Figure 5.

```

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift]
            - halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
    MPI_Isend(build_buffer + start,
            length,
            CS_MPI_REAL,
            halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
            local_rank,
            cs_glob_mpi_comm,
            &(_cs_glob_halo_request[request_count++]));
}
MPI_Waitall(request_count, _cs_glob_halo_request, _cs_glob_halo_status);

```

Figure 5: Pseudo code for data copy in a contiguous buffer in original `cs_halo_sync_var`

The copy is completed when `MPI_Waitall` call finishes as shown in Figure 5.

Modified `cs_halo_sync_var` (version 1)

We first implement a version of the `cs_halo_sync_var` routine using MPI-2.0 one sided communication routines. We use the MPI one sided routine `MPI_Get`. In our implementation we first assemble send buffers for halo exchange into a contiguous buffer as shown in Figure 6

```
same_as_last = 1;
for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
    if (start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] == start)
        same_as_last = same_as_last * 1;
    else{
        start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] = start;
        same_as_last = 0;
    }
    length = halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - start;
    for (i = 0; i < length; i++){
        build_buffer[start + i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];
        buffer_end = start + i;
    }
}
```

Figure 6: Pseudo code for buffer copying in `cs_halo_sync_var` version 1.

The steps in Figure 6 are similar to the steps in Figure 4 of the original `cs_halo_sync_var`. We have introduced additional variables `start_indx_of_send_buff` and `same_as_last` in this section. The `start_indx_of_send_buff` stores the starting index in `build_buffer` for different ranks. `same_as_last = 1` tells that the send buffer lengths are the same between current and previous calls of `cs_halo_sync_var`, while `same_as_last = 0` tells that the send buffer lengths are different between current and previous calls of `cs_halo_sync_var`. This is a rank local operation. Next we check whether `same_as_last` is the same globally as shown in Figure 7.

```
MPI_Allreduce(&same_as_last, &same_as_last_global, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_PROD,
             cs_glob_mpi_comm);
```

Figure 7: Pseudo code for checking whether the send buffer lengths are same between current and previous calls globally in `cs_halo_sync_var` version 1.

The calculation of `same_as_last_global` helps to minimize number of times of new MPI window is created. We create a new communication window only when `same_as_last_global` is 0. In one sided communication the receiver rank should know the memory address in the source rank to fetch data from that location. For this we explicitly receive send buffer address which is stored in `start_indx_of_send_buff` in the sender side. On the receiver side this is stored in `start_indx_of_recv_buff`.

```

if (!same_as_last_global) {
    MPI_Win_create(start_indx_of_send_buff, sz_array*sizeof(int),
                  sizeof(int), MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win1);
    MPI_Win_fence(0, win1);
    for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++)
        if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
            MPI_Get(&start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]],
1, MPI_INT,
                  halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id], local_rank, 1, MPI_INT,
win1);
            MPI_Win_create(build_buffer, (buffer_end)*sizeof(cs_real_t),
sizeof(cs_real_t), MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win);
        }
}

```

Figure 8: Pseudo code for creating MPI window for one sided communication and exchange of memory addresses in `cs_halo_sync_var` version 1.

A procedure of creating an MPI window in Figure 8 is expensive. On the other hand, the send buffer lengths do not change frequently during the simulation run. Hence `same_as_last_global` is 1 in most iterations and consequently the above overhead is minimal. After this operation, `MPI_Get` is posted to receive data.

```

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];
    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
        MPI_Get(var + halo->n_local_elts + start, length, CS_MPI_REAL,
halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id], start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo-
>c_domain_rank[rank_id]], length, CS_MPI_REAL, win);
    }
}

```

Figure 9: Pseudo code for halo exchange in `cs_halo_sync_var` version 1.

The `MPI_get` call in Figure 9 uses `start_indx_of_recv_buff` as the memory address to fetch data from the source rank.

Modified `cs_halo_sync_var` (version 2)

In this version of the routine we try to use a MPI-3.0 routine called `MPI_Rget` [7]. `MPI_Rget` is similar to `MPI_Get`, except that it allocates a communication request object and associates it with the request handle that can be used to wait or test for completion. The use of `MPI_Rget` requires minimal code changes from our version 1 of `cs_halo_sync_var` routine. At the same time `MPI_Rget` gives the possibility of overlapping communication from different ranks. This can reduce the overall communication time. The code remains much the same as `cs_halo_sync_var` version 1. We only modify the data receiving section by replacing `MPI_Get` by `MPI_Rget` and then putting the appropriate `MPI_Waitall` statement at the end as is shown in figure 10.

```

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];
    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
        MPI_Rget(var + halo->n_local_elts + start, length, CS_MPI_REAL,
            halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id], start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo->
            c_domain_rank[rank_id]], length, CS_MPI_REAL, win, req[rank_id]);
    }
}
MPI_Waitall(halo->n_c_domains, req, status);

```

Figure 10: Pseudo code for halo exchange using MPI_Rget in cs_halo_sync_var version 2

4. Results & discussion

For our tests we have taken a test case called ONE_TUBE. The configuration corresponds to the flow in a staggered bundle of tubes, used by Simonin and Barcouda to conduct their experiment [15]. All our tests are done on the Triolith cluster [14] which is an Intel Sandybridge, infiniband cluster.

cs_halo_sync_var (version 1)

We have run our test case on 64, 128, 256 and 512 MPI ranks. We have done correctness checking by comparing results of original run and the modified run. The scaling results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Scaling results for One Tube test case runs

ranks	Total run time (s)		cs_halo_sync_var time (s)	
	original	version 1	original	version 1
64	264.41	264.12	6.6	6.1
128	152.49	152.11	7.3	6.8
256	105.89	105.96	9.2	8.5
512	91.04	91.03	11.3	10.2

As we can see in Table 1 the modified version 1 is slightly faster than the original version of *Code_Saturne*. We have also observed that the modified version has 1 - 2% less memory overhead. This is probably because in the modified version 1 as we are using MPI one sided communication it does not require MPI to allocate internal buffer for communication. This effect will be more prominent in very wide jobs running over several thousand cores. In our tests the routine cs_halo_sync_var is called more than 50000 times. The send buffer lengths in cs_halo_sync_var are changed only a few times during the whole run. As we do not have a clear understanding of when the buffer lengths are changing from the previous iteration we are checking every time whether the send buffer lengths have changed from the previous iteration. This brute force method introduces some extra overhead which can be optimized with better knowledge of the behaviour of the code.

cs_halo_sync_var version 2

In this version we have used MPI-3.0 function MPI_Rget. With mvapich2 we could compile the code but the run crashes as soon as it encounters the MPI_Rget function. We have no clear explanation why this is happening and we could not get any hint from the mvapich2 user guide. We believe the implementation of MPI_Rget function is not yet very robust in mvapich2.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

Appendix A: Code listing for cs_halo_sync_var

```
void
cs_halo_sync_var(const cs_halo_t *halo,
                 cs_halo_type_t sync_mode,
                 cs_real_t var[])
{
    cs_lnum_t i, start, length;

    int local_rank_id = (cs_glob_n_ranks == 1) ? 0 : -1;
    const cs_lnum_t end_shift = (sync_mode == CS_HALO_STANDARD) ? 1 : 2;

#ifdef HAVE_MPI

    if (cs_glob_n_ranks > 1) {

        int rank_id;
        int request_count = 0;
        cs_real_t *build_buffer = (cs_real_t *)_cs_glob_halo_send_buffer;
        const int local_rank = cs_glob_rank_id;
#ifdef CBASU_AT_NSC //Changes by cbasu@nsc.liu.se
#define VERSION 1
#endif
        #if VERSION == 1 // 2nd version, working, speed lightly better than original
            int buffer_end, ii;
            int same_as_last, same_as_last_global;
            static int first_call = 1;
            //static MPI_Group group;
            // the new global variables are now moved to a header file
            /* Assemble buffers for halo exchange; */

            if (first_call) { // this is called only once
                for (i= 0; i < sz_array; i++) {
                    start_indx_of_send_buff[i] = 0;
                    start_indx_of_recv_buff[i] = 0;
                }
                first_call = 0;
                MPI_Comm_group(cs_glob_mpi_comm, &group);
            }

            same_as_last = 1;
            for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {

                if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
                    start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
                    if (start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] == start)
                        same_as_last = same_as_last * 1;
                    else{
                        start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] = start;
                        same_as_last = 0;
                    }
                }
                length = halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - start;

                for (i = 0; i < length; i++){
                    build_buffer[start + i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];
                    buffer_end = start + i;
                }
            }
        #endif
    }
}
```

```

}

TIMER1;
MPI_Allreduce(&same_as_last, &same_as_last_global, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_PROD, cs_glob_mpi_comm);

if (!same_as_last_global) {
    if (win1 != MPI_WIN_NULL)
        MPI_Win_free (&win1);
    MPI_Win_create(start_indx_of_send_buff,      sz_array*sizeof(int),      sizeof(int),
MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win1);
    MPI_Win_fence(0, win1);
    for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++)
        if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
            MPI_Get(&start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]], 1, MPI_INT,
                    halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id], local_rank, 1, MPI_INT, win1);
        }
    MPI_Win_fence(0, win1);

    if (win != MPI_WIN_NULL)
        MPI_Win_free (&win);
    MPI_Win_create(build_buffer,      (buffer_end)*sizeof(cs_real_t),      sizeof(cs_real_t),
MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win);
}
TIMER2;
t_cs_halo_sync_var = t_cs_halo_sync_var + TIME_DIFF;
n_cs_halo_sync_var = n_cs_halo_sync_var + 1;
MPI_Win_fence(0, win);

/* Receive data from distant ranks */
for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
    start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];
    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
        MPI_Get(var + halo->n_local_elts + start, length, CS_MPI_REAL,
                halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
                start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo-
>c_domain_rank[rank_id]], length, CS_MPI_REAL, win);
    }
    else
        local_rank_id = rank_id;
}
MPI_Win_fence(0, win);
#elif VERSION == 2 // MPI 3.0 version, crashes
int      buffer_end, ii;
int      same_as_last, same_as_last_global;
static int first_call = 1;
//static MPI_Group group;
// the new global variables are now moved to a header file
/* Assemble buffers for halo exchange; */

if (first_call) { // this is called only once
    for (i= 0; i < sz_array; i++) {
        start_indx_of_send_buff[i] = 0;
        start_indx_of_recv_buff[i] = 0;
    }
}

```

```

        first_call = 0;
        MPI_Comm_group(cs_glob_mpi_comm, &group);
    }

    same_as_last = 1;
    for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {

        if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
            start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
            if (start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] == start)
                same_as_last = same_as_last * 1;
            else{
                start_indx_of_send_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]] = start;
                same_as_last = 0;
            }
            length = halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - start;

            for (i = 0; i < length; i++){
                build_buffer[start + i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];
                buffer_end = start + i;
            }
        }
    }

    TIMER1;
    MPI_Allreduce(&same_as_last, &same_as_last_global, 1, MPI_INT, MPI_PROD, cs_glob_mpi_comm);

    if (!same_as_last_global) {
        if (win1 != MPI_WIN_NULL)
            MPI_Win_free (&win1);
        MPI_Win_create(start_indx_of_send_buff,      sz_array*sizeof(int),      sizeof(int),
MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win1);
        MPI_Win_fence(0, win1);
        for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++)
            if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
                MPI_Get(&start_indx_of_recv_buff[halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id]], 1, MPI_INT,
                    halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id], local_rank, 1, MPI_INT, win1);
            }
        MPI_Win_fence(0, win1);

        if (win != MPI_WIN_NULL)
            MPI_Win_free (&win);
        MPI_Win_create(build_buffer,      (buffer_end)*sizeof(cs_real_t),      sizeof(cs_real_t),
MPI_INFO_NULL, cs_glob_mpi_comm, &win);
    }
    TIMER2;
    t_cs_halo_sync_var = t_cs_halo_sync_var + TIME_DIFF;
    n_cs_halo_sync_var = n_cs_halo_sync_var + 1;

    MPI_Request req[1000];          // statically allocated, change later
    MPI_Status status[1000];

    /* Receive data from distant ranks */
    for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {
        start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
        length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];
        if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {
            MPI_Rget(var + halo->n_local_elts + start, length, CS_MPI_REAL,

```

```

        halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],                start_idx_of_recv_buff[halo-
>c_domain_rank[rank_id]], length, CS_MPI_REAL, win, &req);
        MPI_Wait(&req, &status);
    }
    else
        local_rank_id = rank_id;
}
MPI_Waitall( halo->n_c_domains, req, status);
#endif
#else
/* Receive data from distant ranks */

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {

    start = halo->index[2*rank_id];
    length = halo->index[2*rank_id + end_shift] - halo->index[2*rank_id];

    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {

        MPI_Irecv(var + halo->n_local_elts + start,
            length,
            CS_MPI_REAL,
            halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
            halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
            cs_glob_mpi_comm,
            &(cs_glob_halo_request[request_count++]));

    }
    else
        local_rank_id = rank_id;
}

/* Assemble buffers for halo exchange;
   with threading, use dynamic scheduling ,as this is probably a small loop */

#pragma omp parallel for private(start, length, i) schedule(dynamic)
for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {

    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {

        start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
        length =  halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift]
            - halo->send_index[2*rank_id];

        for (i = 0; i < length; i++)
            build_buffer[start + i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];

    }

}

/* We wait for posting all receives (often recommended) */

if (cs_glob_halo_use_barrier)

```

```

    MPI_Barrier(cs_glob_mpi_comm);

/* Send data to distant ranks */

for (rank_id = 0; rank_id < halo->n_c_domains; rank_id++) {

    if (halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id] != local_rank) {

        start = halo->send_index[2*rank_id];
        length =  halo->send_index[2*rank_id + end_shift]
                - halo->send_index[2*rank_id];

        MPI_Isend(build_buffer + start,
                length,
                CS_MPI_REAL,
                halo->c_domain_rank[rank_id],
                local_rank,
                cs_glob_mpi_comm,
                &(_cs_glob_halo_request[request_count++]));

    }

}

/* Wait for all exchanges */

MPI_Waitall(request_count, _cs_glob_halo_request, _cs_glob_halo_status);
#endif
}
#endif /* defined(HAVE_MPI) */

/* Copy local values in case of periodicity */

if (halo->n_transforms > 0) {

    if (local_rank_id > -1) {

        cs_real_t *recv_var
            = var + halo->n_local_elts + halo->index[2*local_rank_id];

        start = halo->send_index[2*local_rank_id];
        length =  halo->send_index[2*local_rank_id + end_shift]
                - halo->send_index[2*local_rank_id];

        for (i = 0; i < length; i++)
            recv_var[i] = var[halo->send_list[start + i]];

    }

}

}

```